

LANGUAGE VARIETIES AND DIALECTS ARE AN INTEGRAL PART OF PLURILINGUAL COMPETENCE

Isanova Zebuniso Shavkatovna

PhD student of Uzbekistan State University of world
languages, Tashkent Uzbekistan

E-mail: zebunisoisanova7@gmail.com

Tel: +99833 3588086

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Annotation: This article highlights the importance of English varieties in improving plurilingual competence in English.

Key words: Language varieties, dialects, plurilingual competence, native speaker, American English, British English.

The concept of plurilingualism refers not only to languages, but also to relations within the same language variants or dialects .

Galante states that, plurilingual is someone who knows two or more languages, but does not necessarily speak them at the same level; for example, one language may be more fluent than another. Also, a plurilingual person is a person who knows the variants (dialects) of the same language, for example, how the language is used in different regions of the country, or in other countries.

In foreign language teaching and the improvement of plurilingual competence, it is appropriate to include the language variants or dialects being studied, as such knowledge is important in increasing students' understanding of languages and cultural diversity.

Today's trends in English language learning and teaching and the goal of plurilingualism and plurilingual competence are encouraging English speakers to develop communicative competence in English in its various variants worldwide. Considering the lingua franca of English, it has been repeatedly pointed out that the standardized "native speaker" model does not justify itself.

Language learners need to be sensitive to the different norms and variants of global English and to develop plurilingual competence. Because today, English speakers and users around the world, even most native speakers, do not know the widely taught varieties "British English" and "American English". Because even native English speakers rarely speak very generalized traditional English.

As a result of globalization, the function of English as an international medium calls for a rethinking of English language classes.

It includes not only the understanding of different language varieties, but also the knowledge of other cultures, the ability to adequately respond to the problems arising from the culture, and the differences between language learners and encounters in international communication.

Currently English has different varieties in different regions of the world. These variants differ in vocabulary, grammar, speech, accent, tone, intonation, spelling, etc.

For example, if we look at American and British English, the biggest difference is in the vocabulary of American English.

Example,

American English	British English
elevator	lift
faucet	tap
apartment	flat

But there are also significant differences in grammar, phonetics and other aspects.

The major differences in other varieties of English are seen in other aspects. For example, the differences in grammar between Indian and African varieties of English are obvious.

But from the point of view of communicative competence, it is argued that differences between varieties of English are not necessary (Trudgill and Hannah 2002; Jenkins 2003)

Students need to learn about the phonetic differences of as many varieties as possible. This increases their communication efficiency in different language options.

It is important for English language learners to know the differences between English variants in their use of the language, as it helps them to understand English as it is used around the world. Another aspect of the problem is that there are many English speakers or users around the world today. That is, the majority of English users today are non-native speakers. Today, English is diverse, with less use of the highly generalized Traditional Standard English. And this in turn means bringing more options to English language teaching.

In the teaching of English, it is proposed to focus on the development of the awareness of the world Englishes (Ates, B., Eslami, Z., Wright, K. L., Kumaravadivelu, B, Canagarajah, S., Crystal , D). That is, they emphasized the need to pay attention to the teaching of English as a pluricentric language and to

reflect the characteristics of different variants (multivariant) of English curriculum (Sadeghpour M., Sharifian F., Cenoz J., Gorter D., Bieswanger M.)

Some researchers have even advocated abandoning the native-speaker standard altogether (Jenkins 2005; Seidlhofer 2005).

References:

1. Ates, B., Eslami, Z., & Wright, K. L. (2015). Incorporating world Englishes into undergraduate ESL education courses. *World Englishes*, 34(3), 485–501.
2. Kumaravadivelu, B. (2012). Individual identity, cultural globalization & teaching English as an international language: A case for epistemic break. In L. Alsagoff, S. L. McKay, G. Hu, & W. A. Renandya (Eds.), *Principles and practices for teaching English as an international language* (pp. 9–27). London: Routledge.
3. Canagarajah, S. (2006). Changing communicative needs, revised assessment objectives: Testing English as an international language. *Language Assessment Quarterly*, 3(3), 229–242.
4. Crystal, D. (2003). *English as a global language* (2nd ed.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
5. Sadeghpour M., Sharifian F. *World Englishes in English language teaching //World Englishes*. – 2019. – T. 38. – №. 1-2. – C. 245-258.
6. Cenoz J., Gorter D. *Towards a plurilingual approach in English language teaching: Softening the boundaries between languages //Tesol Quarterly*. – 2013. – T. 47. – №. 3. – C. 591-599.
7. Bieswanger M. *Varieties of English in current English language teaching //Stellenbosch Papers in Linguistics*. – 2008. – T. 38. – №. 1. – C. 27-47.
8. Seidlhofer B. *English as a lingua franca //ELT journal*. – 2005. – T. 59. – №. 4. – C. 339-341.
9. Jenkins J. *Teaching pronunciation for English as a lingua franca: A sociopolitical perspective //The globalisation of English and the English language classroom*. – 2005. – C. 145-158.

